

EIJASTR

EUROPEAN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF APPLIED SCIENCES AND THEORETICAL RESEARCH

International Scientific Journal

2026

European International Journal Of Applied Sciences And Theoretical Research

Volume 02, Issue 06

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MEDICAL AND BIOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF WOMEN'S SPORTS

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the study of problems in women's sports. This paper examines the effects of physical exercises on the female body in traditional and "non-traditional" sports. Biological differences between men and women are analyzed, and the necessity of considering these differences when choosing sports specialization and planning differentiated training loads is substantiated.

Keywords: football, boxing, judo, kurash, cup, women, training, analysis, homeostasis, work capacity, endurance.

Introduction. Caring for women's health is one of the most important responsibilities of our state. The role of women in all spheres of society is steadily increasing. At the end of the twentieth century and the beginning of the twenty-first century, the process of feminization intensified in many countries of the world, and women now constitute nearly half of the population. Women actively participate alongside men in all fields of industry, agriculture, science, and culture.

Feminization has also influenced the field of sports. The number of sports practiced by women continues to grow steadily. For example, while only two sports for women were included in the program of the first modern Olympic Games, today their number has reached nearly eighty. Women are now successfully participating in sports previously considered exclusive to men, such as football, boxing, judo, freestyle wrestling, and ultra-long-distance running.

The famous women's handball team Spartak Kyiv won the European Champions Cup thirteen times, and this achievement still remains a record. In competitive swimming, the world records achieved by female Olympic athletes have approached the standards required for the title of Master of Sport among men.

Today, there is no doubt that regular engagement in physical education and sports, as well as scientifically organized training processes, contributes to the harmonious physical development of the female body and promotes a healthy lifestyle. Adequate physical activity positively affects the circulatory, respiratory, and metabolic systems, strengthens the body's defense mechanisms, and slows down the aging process.

Physically trained women demonstrate greater resistance to diseases, enhanced adaptive capacities, and safer pregnancy and childbirth processes. However, excessive physical loads in elite sports may, in some cases, negatively affect the female body.

The achievements of the world's strongest female athletes demonstrate that attaining record-level results requires not only high physical abilities but also strong willpower, determination, and psychological resilience.

At present, the adaptive reactions of the female body to changes in external and internal environments have not been sufficiently studied. The most active research on women's sports was mainly conducted during the 1960s–1980s.

These studies investigated differences between men and women in physical qualities, psychological indicators, stress resistance, working capacity, endurance, and functional condition.

Participation in “non-traditional” sports affects the female body in different ways. Some studies have revealed that women practicing judo experience an increased number of severe injuries, higher testosterone levels, and decreased estrogen levels.

Among female athletes engaged in ultra-long-distance running, testosterone levels have been observed to reach the threshold of clinical pathology. This raises concerns regarding possible negative effects on reproductive system function.

Football, however, is distinguished by the fact that it does not exert serious negative effects on women's health, and the frequency of injuries is lower compared to men.

Sports such as rhythmic gymnastics, volleyball, tennis, and swimming are considered among the most beneficial for the female body. They not only help form a beautiful and proportionate physique but also develop aerobic energy metabolism systems.

Sexual dimorphism refers to the combination of genetic, anatomical, physiological, and psychological differences between men and women.

Table 1

Comparative Indicators of the Structural Components of Female and Male Organisms

Cohort	bone tissue (%)	muscle tissue (%)	adipose tissue (%)
middle-aged women	16	36	18–25
middle-aged men	18	42	12
trained female athletes	14	42–45	10–15
trained male athletes	20–21	45–50	10–11

As can be seen from the table data, men have a higher muscle mass, while women have a relatively higher proportion of adipose tissue. This condition has a direct impact on physical working capacity and endurance characteristics.

From an anatomical perspective, women have a more delicate skeletal structure, lower muscle mass, and a higher proportion of adipose tissue. In men, the muscular system is more developed; therefore, women's physical working capacity is estimated to be approximately 60–80% of that of men. However, women often demonstrate superiority in endurance and flexibility.

Training loads in elite sports are considered extreme conditions for the human body. In female athletes, it is important to take into account the phases of the menstrual cycle when planning training loads.

According to research, the highest level of working capacity is observed in the postmenstrual and post-ovulatory phases. These periods are considered the most favorable for developing strength, speed, and endurance abilities.

In women, adaptation to physical loads occurs based on the principle of energy conservation. However, constant stress in sports may lead to overstrain of the nervous system.

Coaches and sports physicians face the task of minimizing the negative effects of sports on the female body. Therefore, in sports selection, it is necessary to consider individual biological capabilities, as well as phenotypic and genotypic characteristics.

Conclusion. It is impossible to fully address all issues related to women's sports within a single article. The process of training women in elite sports requires a deep consideration of the specific biological characteristics of the female body.

The differentiated organization of the training process, the identification of natural abilities using modern methods, and the prevention of negative consequences of sports are among the most pressing issues in women's sports.

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